

The Influence of Photovoltaic Models and Battery Models in System Simulation and Optimization

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Abstract

Selecting accurate and robust models is important for simulation and optimization of a clean energy system. This paper compares two photovoltaic (PV) models and two battery models in an open-source code, Opti-CE. The PV models are single diode model and its simplified model. The battery models are Improved Shepherd model and energy balance model. The models are compared from a perspective of overall system simulation and optimization in particular on both accuracy and computational time. The results indicate that simplified PV model causes 0.86% normalized root mean square error (nRMSE) compared with the single diode model, while decreases the simulation time from more than 800s to less than 0.01s. The energy balance battery model reduces simulation time from more than 5s to less than 0.03s. The energy balance model tends to underestimate the battery State of Charge (SOC) compared with the Improved Shepherd model. However, the error is not accumulative during the simulation. Compared to the Pareto front with single diode model and Improved Shepherd model, the simplified PV model increases the Pareto front values and result in both higher Self Sufficiency Ratio (SSR) and Net Present Value (NPV), while the energy balance battery model decreases the part of Pareto front, where individuals have low NPV.

Keywords: photovoltaic; battery; optimization; genetic algorithm;

1. Introduction

The 2 Degree Celsius (2DS) scenario and the aggravated environmental issues urge the transformation of energy systems [1]. During the transformation process, the simulation and optimization of the energy systems are vitally important. The optimal combination and design of different components and operation strategies can benefit the energy system in achieving higher economic value [2], higher renewable energy penetration level [3] as well as other system performance indicators [4]. There are some available software or tools, which include both commercial and open-source. However, a common limitation is that these software or tools provide little space for users to customize and incorporate modules that are not in the built-in library. Another limitation is that optimization is not always included. Researchers from Mälardalen University and KTH-Royal Institute of Technology have released Opti-CE [5], an open-source code based on Matlab® environment. Opti-CE aims at simulating clean energy systems and performing single or multiple objective optimizations. Photovoltaic and battery are some of core modules in Opti-CE. Previous studies compared different PV models and battery models, respectively. Hu et al.

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studied different equivalent circuit models for Li-ion batteries [6]. Ramadesigan et al. investigated battery models ranging from empirical models to molecular/atomistic models [7]. Tossa et al. [8] and Dolara et al. [9] carried out comparative research about selecting PV models. However, the focuses of the above studies are all related to specific modules. The influence of selecting different models on the overall system performance shall be further studied.

This study aims to compare two different PV models and battery models and analyze their influences on the optimization results. In the first place, the PV models and battery models are compared separately in terms of simulation accuracy and time. Their influence of different models on the system optimization is carried out in the following section. Suggestions about employing the different models are given during the analyzing of the result.

2. Methodology

2.1. Schematic diagram of the simulated and optimized energy system

The studied energy system is based on building application with PV and storage (DC side). The system is also connected to electricity grid. The inverter is placed between AC side and DC side for conversion. The load and weather data is recorded from a residential building in Gothenburg, Sweden.

The objectives of the optimization problem are to maximize Self Sufficiency Ratio (SSR) and maximize the Net Present Value (NPV). The decisional variables include component capacity and PV installation angles (Tilt and Azimuth angles). The multi-objective problem is solved with Genetic Algorithm. The optimization results are presented in the form of Pareto fronts. The study is carried out with Opti-CE. The local environment is Matlab R2015b, which is installed in a Windows 8 desktop with i7 processor and 32GB memory.

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of the system

2.2. PV models

Based on the isotropic diffuse model, the radiation on the tilted surface include three components: beam, isotropic diffuse and solar radiation diffusely reflected from the ground [10]:

$$G_t = G_b R_{beam} + G_d \frac{1+\cos\beta}{2} + G\rho \frac{1+\cos\beta}{2} \quad (1)$$

The effective absorbed solar ratio is obtained with Equation 2 [10]:

$$\frac{S}{S_{ref}} = M \left(\frac{G_b}{G_{ref}} R_{beam} K_{\tau\alpha,b} + \frac{G_d}{G_{ref}} K_{\tau\alpha,d} \frac{1+\cos\beta}{2} + \frac{G}{G_{ref}} \rho K_{\tau\alpha,g} \frac{1+\cos\beta}{2} \right) \quad (2)$$

where, $K_{\tau\alpha}$ is the incidence angle modifier, β is the tilt angel, and R_{beam} is the ratio factor.

2.2.1. Single diode five parameter model

In the single diode model, the equivalent circuit, which represents individual cell, consists of current source, single diode, and resistors. The circuit is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Single Diode Model

The maximal power point (MPP) can be determined with Equations 3 and 4.

$$I_{mp} = I_{PH} - I_0 \left[e^{\frac{V_{mp} + I_{mp} \cdot R_s}{a}} - 1 \right] - \frac{V_{mp} + I_{mp} \cdot R_s}{R_{sh}} \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{I_{mp}}{V_{mp}} = \frac{\frac{I_0}{a} \cdot e^{\left(\frac{V_{mp} + I_{mp} \cdot R_s}{a}\right)} + \frac{1}{R_{sh}}}{1 + \frac{R_s}{R_{sh}} + \frac{I_0 R_s}{I_0} \cdot e^{\left(\frac{V_{mp} + I_{mp} \cdot R_s}{a}\right)}} \quad (4)$$

where, I_{PH} , I_0 , a , R_{sh} are variables that depend on the radiation on the tilted surface (G_t), effective absorbed solar ratio (S/S_{ref}) and cell temperature (T_c). The detailed calculation method can be found in equations 23.2.8-12 from Duffie and Beckman [10].

The PV module cell temperature estimation depends on the thermal process modeling. In literature there are many approaches. For instance, Ma et al. uses the module back-surface temperature to estimate the cell temperature [11]; Neises et al. develops a thermal models and corrects the NOCT temperature [12]. In this study, the cell temperature is estimated with Equation 5 [11]:

$$\frac{T_c - T_a}{NOCT - 20} = \frac{G}{800} \cdot \frac{9.5}{5.7 + 3.8V} \cdot \left[1 - \frac{\eta_c}{(\tau\alpha)} \right] \quad (5)$$

where, V is the local wind speed, and η_c is efficiency of the PV module.

The PV single diode model is solved through iteration. The cell temperature is obtained at first with the initial guess of η_c . Then I_{PH} , I_0 , a and R_{sh} are computed. Equations 3 and 4 are then solved to get the updated η_c , which is provided to the next iteration until reaching the iteration stop criteria. The process is time consuming because a numerical approach is employed.

2.2.2. Simplified PV model

Duffie and Beckman[10] proposed a simplified method in estimating the PV power production. The method calculates the power production through correcting the PV module efficiency under different weather input (Equations 6-9):

$$P_{PV} = \eta_{PV} \cdot A_{PV} \cdot G \cdot \quad (6)$$

$$\eta_{PV} = \eta_{PV,STC} \left[1 + \frac{\mu}{\eta_{PV,STC}} (T_c - T_{STC}) \right] \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{T_c - T_a}{NOCT - 20} = \frac{G}{800} \cdot \frac{9.5}{5.7 + 3.8V} \cdot \left[1 - \frac{\eta_c}{(\tau\alpha)} \right] \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{\eta_c}{(\tau\alpha)} = \eta_{PV,STC} \quad (9)$$

where, μ is the temperature coefficient of the output power, and it is approximated as:

$$\mu \approx \eta_{PV,STC} \frac{\mu_{V_{OC}}}{V_{mpp,STC}} \quad (10)$$

$\mu_{V_{OC}}$ is the open circuit voltage temperature coefficient. With another assumption that $\frac{\eta_c}{(\tau\alpha)}$ is approximated as $\eta_{PV,STC}$, equations 7-10 are merged into equation 11:

$$\eta_{PV} = \eta_{PV,STC} \left[1 + \frac{\mu}{\eta_{PV,STC}} (T_a - T_{STC}) + \frac{\mu}{\eta_{PV,STC}} \cdot \frac{(NOCT -)}{800} \cdot \frac{9.5}{5.7+3.8V} (1 - \eta_{PV,STC}) G_t \right] \quad (11)$$

The reduced method requires neither iteration nor numerical solution, thus requiring much less computational resource.

2.3. Battery models

2.3.1. Improved Shepherd Model

Improved Shepherd model, developed by Tremblay et al [13, 14], is used in this study. The charging and discharging voltage-current relationship are represented by Equations 12 and 13, respectively:

$$V = E_0 - K \frac{Q}{Q - \int it} \cdot i^* - K \frac{Q}{Q - \int it} \int it + A \cdot e^{-B \cdot \int it} - i \cdot R \quad (12)$$

$$V = E_0 - K \frac{Q}{0.1Q + \int it} \cdot i^* - K \frac{Q}{Q - \int it} \int it + A \cdot e^{-B \cdot \int it} - i \cdot R \quad (13)$$

The characteristic parameters are taken from Tremblay et al [14]. The battery is constrained to operate within certain voltage and current range, which are 3.0-4.0 V and -0.76-0.76 A for a single cell.

2.3.2. Energy balance model

In some studies, batteries are represented by energy balance model (equation 14):

$$SOC_t = SOC_{t-1} - \sigma_{sd} - P \cdot \eta \quad (14)$$

The approach approximates battery with fixed efficiency. In this model, the maximal charge and discharge rate are constrained to a specific set value, which is 1/3 of the battery capacity per hour.

3. Results and Discussions

3.1. PV module PV model comparison in accuracy and computational time

The yearly PV production from a single panel is simulated under tilt and azimuth angles of 36° and 0°. The corresponding PV production from single diode model and simplified PV models at the same time interval is shown in Fig. 3 (a). The results indicate that the simplified PV model overestimates the production. Moreover, the error enlarges between 10 and 100 Wh. nRMSE (normalized Root Mean Square Error) is obtained as 0.86% with equation 15.

$$nRMSE = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{1}{8760} \sum_{m=1}^{8760} |P_{reduced,m} - P_{1diode,m}|^2}}{\max(P_{1diode,m})} \cdot 100 \quad (15)$$

The simulation is repeated 10 times, the averaged simulation time for the two models is shown in Fig. 3(b). The single diode model takes much more time than the simplified model. During optimization with genetic algorithm, the simulation will be repeated with different input variables. Considering the population size (larger than 100) and generation numbers (larger than 200), it is suggested that the single diode model is not appropriate for the optimization that has tilt and azimuth angles as variables.

Fig. 3. (a) PV production and (b) simulation time from two PV models.

3.2. Influence of azimuth and tilt angles on the optimization

In this section, the effect of excluding tilt and azimuth angles during the optimization on the Pareto front is discussed. The optimization with consideration of only PV capacity and battery capacity is firstly carried out. During the optimization, the tilt and azimuth angles are set as 36° and 0°, under which PV panels has the maximal yearly production for the selected location. The optimization with four variables (PV capacity, battery capacity, azimuth angle and tilt angle) is then carried out. The individuals that makes up the Pareto front of the second optimization are replaced with tilt and azimuth angles of 36° and 0°, forming a new group of individuals. These individuals' SSR and NPV are calculated and also shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. The influence of tilt and azimuth angles on the optimization

The comparison is conducted with both the energy balance and Improved Shepherd battery models. The three SSR-NPV curves coincide with each other. The results indicate that the excluding tilt and azimuth angles have little or no influence on the Pareto front. It is suggested that the overall optimization that includes both capacities and angles as variables can be separated into two steps. The optimal tilt and azimuth angles can be obtained with the purpose of achieving the maximal yearly production at first. The production profile from unit capacity PV panel at the optimal installation angles are then fed to the next-

step optimization, which optimizes the PV capacity through a multi-objective genetic algorithm. The approach can avoid high computational time when using the single diode model.

3.3. Battery model comparison

With 200 kW_p PV and 100 kWh battery, the system simulation is carried out with the two different battery models. The corresponding SOC (State of Charge) from different battery models at the same time interval is shown in Fig. 5. The comparison is carried out with both single diode PV model (Fig. 5a) and simplified PV model (Fig. 5b). The Improved Shepherd battery model shows lower SOC than the energy balance model. The error is not accumulative since occasionally the battery is fully charged (100%) or discharged (20%). What should be noticed is that the battery efficiency in the energy balance model can be calibrated to be more consistent with the Improved Shepherd Model. The battery model simulation time is shown in Fig. 6. The energy balance model takes much less time than the Improved Shepherd model (0.03s vs 6s). However, the Improved Shepherd model is still acceptable in optimization. It takes around 19 hours if assume the optimization is carried out with population size of 150, generation of 300 and 4 parallel workers.

Fig. 5. Battery SOC profile comparison between different battery models

Fig. 6. Different Battery Model Simulation Time

3.4. Pareto Fronts with different PV and Battery models

Multi-objective optimization is carried out for the investigated system with different PV and battery models. The optimization variables are PV capacity and battery capacity. The obtained Pareto fronts are shown in Fig. 7. The Pareto front values with simplified PV model is higher than that with single diode model. The Pareto front values with energy balance battery model is lower than that with Improved Shepherd model when the individuals have relatively low NPV. For the individuals with high NPV value, the effect of employing different battery models is small. Because the energy balance battery model and simplified PV model bring about counteractive effects to the Pareto front, it is noted that the Pareto front with both simplified models fits better with the Pareto front with both detailed models than that with single simplified model.

Fig. 7. Pareto front with different Battery and PV models

4. Conclusion

The study compares two PV models and two battery models from the perspective of overall system simulation and optimization. The results show that the simplified PV model overestimates the production (0.86% nRMSE), while it takes much less simulation time (0.002s) than the single diode model (841s). The Improved Shepherd battery model takes more simulation time (6s) than the energy balance model (0.03s); however, it is generally applicable to be employed in the optimization. The energy balance model tends to have lower SOC than the Improved Shepherd model.

It is more favorable to use the single diode model and Improved Shepherd model in the optimization than the simplified ones, because they are generally more accurate. An approach that avoids much computational time when employing the single diode PV model is proposed. The approach separates the overall optimization process into two consecutive steps. The optimal tilt and azimuth angles should be optimized in the first place. The optimization with PV and battery capacities are then conducted.

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Biography

Yang Zhang is a Ph.D. student in KTH-Royal Institute of Technology. His research focuses on the integration and optimization of energy storage with microgrid. He is one of the main developers of the open-source code Opti-CE. (www.optice.net)